

Imprisonment in Czech Republic as society's service, its aims, and responsibilities

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ABSTRACT: This paper focuses on people in imprisonment and their successful return to society and their life. Imprisonment in Czech Republic has two main aims: provide security and safety and provide social support for those who violated law. Specialised employees focused on penitentiary therapy and care which aims to help to sentenced people to understand their behaviour and problems within overstepping the law. The goal is to not only punish, but mainly to change their attitude and behaviour towards society's law so that they can return to society and become its active and fulfilled members after their release. Mainly the understanding of moral norms, skills, and knowledge is stressed during the imprisonment. Thus, after they are released, they can have independent life. This includes practical skills and abilities as well as social adaptation which are crucial for successful re-integration to society with minimal risk of recidivism.

Keywords: Academy of Prison service of Czech Republic, re-socialisation, Prison service of Czech Republic, handling program, imprisonment, educational and preparation of employees.

Introduction

Current Content of Education in Imprisonment

Structure and Organization of Imprisonment in Czech Republic

Re-Socializing Process during Imprisonment

Conclusion

References

1. Introduction

There is a prison service system in every society which reflects current social, economic, and cultural conditions. This system adapts to own socio-cultural and economic situation in given society. Imprisonment is assumed to be necessary social service with adequate security elements. The crucial sense for effective functioning has educated and qualified personnel who provides quality social services to sentenced individual with regards to law. Further, well-educated personnel have crucial influence on behavioural work with prisoners and their secured return to society.

It is important to realise that all prisoners are human beings with their human and inhabitant rights which must be respected and fulfilled. Their crime and reasons for their imprisonment are not relevant hence they are still human beings with right to protect their human dignity. This must be reflected by prison's employees.

Social exclusion is discussed by Daněk, Klugerová (2023). Social exclusion is a major issue that modern society is attempting to address. It has negative impacts not only on a local level but also on a national, European, and even global scale. In today's interconnected society, it is important to recognize that social exclusion issues in other countries or on other continents will have an impact on us. Therefore, it is crucial to strive for the elimination, prevention, and combat of social exclusion through all possible means.

Every imprisonment system originates gradually in consequence of social factors meeting other social factors. Thus, the imprisonment systems have historical breeding and experiences that influence it till today. Therefore, understanding to this historical context has significant influence for further development and understanding to these services.

With regard to the current conditions prevailing in Czech prisons, I believe that it is now appropriate to place primary emphasis on external connections with sociology and gradually build a position for a possible future return of sociologists to everyday life practice behind the bars of Czech prisons. Sociology must gain in the eyes of the representatives the (partially) lost trust of the Czech prison system. The implementation above contributes to this mentioned researches in which sociologists participated externally and which contribute to the creation of a positive image of sociology. It is better to invest limited resources in external cooperation and gradually strengthen mutual ties (Dirga, 2021).

Crises are very creeping; slowly or quickly. In order to be able to respond adequately to crises, we need to identify control and border (critical) points in good time. These points will then help us to detect impending dangers in time and take appropriate action. The contribution of the article is a description of the existence and illustrative graphical representation of these points, which are crucial for early recognition. When searching for and evaluating threats, it is necessary to analyze their time course and impacts depending on time. The contribution, in contrast to static observation or examination of crises (reaching a critical, further irreversible point), provides an insight into the dynamic side of the crisis. In practice, the symptoms of an impending crisis are either overestimated or not observed at all. The paper newly introduces various parameters, characteristics of crises, which can be used to further classify crises (Rak, Sulc, Kopencova, Vlach, Hudecova, 2022).

Prison research is key to understanding and improving the functioning of this system as a social service. Prisons play a vital role not only in punishment, but also in the rehabilitation and reintegration of prisoners into society.

2. Current Content of Education in Imprisonment

The expectation and content of imprisonment education historically originates and develops based on state attitude towards imprisonment system, philosophical opinions in justice area mainly in imprisonment services. In context of democratic legal state imprisonment becomes crucial social services for public with required security contexts.

The aim of work in imprisonment services is to prepare with adequate form the prisoners to their return to society. The main goal is to prepare and provide adequate conditions for prisoned people so they can return to society and become an active member (reintegrate).

Prisons' personnel should help to prisoned people to familiarise and internalise habits, attitudes, and skills which they will need during their life outside of the prison (re-socialising process).

All these aims should be met in prison where the condition are human, prisoned people are respected, and their rights and freedom are respected. Further, the law and rules are respected as well.

Thus, to be able to change an individual the whole system of imprisonment must be transformed. That means for example, acceptance of international norms and law. Afterwards, the effective and efficient work with prisoners can begin. Further, that will lead to successful process of re-socialisation which will lead towards lower recidivism.

3. Structure and Organization of Imprisonment in Czech Republic

Every society state their system of law and fulfilment of sentences which reflects current needs and values of society. In this system is therefore significant part the imprisonment which have two main aims: protects the society before the delinquents and prepare the sentenced people for their return to the society as regular society member who can respect laws and rules given by society.

The Prison Services of Czech Republic are security corps supervised by Ministry of Justice and it secures the imprisonment and its fulfilment, fulfilment of detention, security in court and correctness during courts. In Czech Republic there are 35 prisons, in which 10 are remands prisons and 25 prisons. Further, the prison service oversees 3 institutes for securing remands. These institutes are prisons for people with mental disability due to which they are not legally responsible. These institutes secure detention and they are type of security detention currently there are 3 institutes which are in Brno, Opava, and Prague.

In Starz pod Ralskem the Prison Services of Czech Republic has educational institution – The Academy of Prison Services of Czech Republic. The Academy aims to provide education and training for new members of prison services. Further, to provide specialised courses and life-long learning courses for employees. For imprisoned people is High School specialised on handcrafts in Prague which runs diverse educational institutions in chosen prisons in Czech Republic.

According to law the Czech's prison personnel is divided into two categories member who serve in uniform and civic employees. Member mainly fulfil security tasks such as security of buildings, prisoners' escorts, and directs supervisions of prisoners. Further, there are justice guards who supervise the behaviour and security at courts, and Ministry buildings.

Whereas the civic employees are specialised workers who are in direct contacts with prisoners such as social workers, psychologists, special pedagogues, medical staff, administrative staff, and supportive staff. The complete number of employees was in December 2023 11 259 employees and that were 7060 members and 4199 civic employees (see table 1.)

(Table 1)

4. Re-Socializing Process during Imprisonment

Law is very strict and states the aims of imprisonment process which are to protect the society in front of delinquents, limit the recidivism and to change behaviour of sentenced. The prison services in Czech Republic focuses on aspects of security as well as on aspects re-socialisation process.

Resocialisation is process which begins immediately when the sentenced become to prison and its aim is to prepare sentenced for their return to society and to provide them with skills so that they can avoid to recidivism. This goal is hard due to the high number of recidivism and addictions which are frequent within sentenced people.

Thus, there are diverse programs provided for sentenced people which can prepare them for their life after their imprisonment ends. These programs offer diverse activities where sentenced individual can practice and gain diverse skills and attitudes needed for successful return to society.

Handling programs is divided into:

- Work activities,
- Educational activities,
- Special educational activities,
- Activities of interest,
- Areas of outside relationships creation.

Work activities.

Work activities are crucial part of the handling program. The prisoners have work responsibility if they are placed into the work activities with regards to their health, age, work abilities and skills. The aim of these activities is to provide chance to build work attitude mainly for those who never worked and keep this attitude. Work in prison offers chance to earn money which pay for their stay in prison and to cover compensation for their crime.

Educational activities

Education is crucial during resocialisation of sentenced people. These activities are focused on gaining knowledge and skills for successful return to society. The Prison Service of Czech Republic tries to secure that sentenced people have chance to get education during their imprisonment. To meet this there are educational centres in prisons which offer diverse majors. Further, it is possible to take courses provided by external companies which helps to gain specific education which can be used after return to society.

Throughout the COVID-19 pandemic there has been a corner of society where the spotlight has not fallen – the black hole of prisons, confining predominantly poor, minoritised and often younger adults. Globally, during the pandemic, people detained in prison have been locked away in solitary, or near solitary, confinement for up to 23-hours a day. In the UK, this meant choosing between fresh air, exercise or a phone call to loved ones each day. There has been little mention of education. Those in custody endured over a year locked in a cell without access to basic education let alone Higher Education (HE). In examining the state's responsibility to provide "education for all", we demonstrate, through our collective participation in the Inside-Out Prison Exchange Programme, the value and importance of prison education beyond the current focus on risk, responsibility and recidivism. We evidence the transformative and humanising potential of HE in prison through three key elements – the space and learning environment; the role of voice, recognition and agency; and the power of disruptive and transgressive teaching practice. We shine a light on education in prison during the COVID-19 pandemic. The impacts of COVID-19 expose new and deeper forms of structural disadvantage that shape the educational experiences and journeys of people in custody. We consider how we can expedite "education as the practice of freedom" for those who are incarcerated during and beyond the pandemic. We conclude by reimagining HE in UK prisons, reflecting upon alternative, more positive, approaches to prison education (Martin, Bowl, Banks, 2023).

Special educational activities

These activities are focused on understanding of causes and consequences of offences, risks and needs of each sentenced individual. These include psychological and therapeutical activities which lead to right resocialisation and supports and individual's development. The Prison Service of Czech Republic tries to perform these activities in specialised centres where sentenced people have some type of mental disability, behavioural disorders, personal disorders, or addictions.

Activities of interest

These are focused on sensible usage of leisure time during imprisonment. They aimed to improve and develop skills and social abilities which supports limitation of recidivism. Favourite activities are sports, condition activities, handcrafts activities, and participation diverse leisure time clubs.

We can also include support for spiritual needs here. Among the most problematic issues are issues of pragmatic faith, obstacles preventing prison chaplains from performing their jobs, and the unsystematic and inconsistent nature of prison and post-penitentiary spiritual care (Dirga, Váně, 2020).

Areas of outside relationships creation

This area is focused on active creation of relationships, their strengthening, and supporting of social relationships of sentenced people with their families and friends outside of the prison. The aim is for the sentenced people to develop their skills and abilities in area of social communication which will them during their transition from prison to their life after release.

Employees of Prison Service of Czech Republic the civic employees as well as the members work in direct contact with prisoners who have experienced repeated conflicts with law. Plus, the prisoners are often complicated personas several numbers of prisoners have some type of personal disorders, or they have some type of addictions either drugs, alcohol, or gambling. Therefore, if the employees of the prison services should work with prisoners and their diverse personal characteristics it is crucial that they are aware of these pathological influences which often are causes of their delinquent behaviour.

The imprisonment of sentenced people has its purpose and sense. Mainly to protect members of society against the criminal behaviour and prepare prisoners for their life after their releasement. Therefore, the employees prepare programs that reflect the seriousness of the crime, the length of the imprisonment, and mainly they aim to prepare the prisoners for their life after their releasement, so they can become fulfilled members of society. Thus, the programs should reflect the diverse needs of prisoners.

The success of the program depends on several factors such as prisoner inner motivation but also on the professional qualities of the employees. Therefore, significant stress is put on professionals and their characteristics. Thus, the employees must be able to handle the stress, unordinary of their work and environment they work. Further, they must be able to stay immune against the pressure to reveal some information, advantages, and breaking inner and outside rules given by the prison environment.

Education and training of employees of The Prison services of Czech Republic

The Academy in Straz pod Ralskem is the only centre of The Prison Services of Czech Republic where all employees, the civic and well as the members complete primary specific courses and further the specialised courses in life-long learning.

The Academy in its activity cooperate with specialists in the area mainly from area of secure escorts of prisoners and universities. The cooperation is done through conducting diverse seminars, conferences, and work-based meetings. The Academy also participates in development of academia work and research in area of pathology and penitentiary.

A quality education that responds flexibly to changes in the educational needs of pupils and students at all levels of education, as well as to the demands of future employers on the labour market, must become Czech Republic's priority. It plays an important role in tackling unemployment, as well as in the economic development and the increase in competitiveness of our country (Tomšíková, Němejc, Smékalová, 2019).

The Academy create for the needs of prisoner services own system of education and preparation which is dedicated for every employee and professional group. Every new

member of civic employee must go through expertise preparation, then they complete specialised course and education for their role.

The primary preparation is aimed for all employees whether they are civic employees or member of prison services. For the members of prison services is one type of the primary course but within the civic employees their preparation depends on whether they will be in direct contact with prisoner and if they will be part of the handling program.

Individual aspects (problems, trends, topics) of prison systems are in the long-term interests of penitentiary sociologists and penologists, which also applies to the situation in the countries of Central Europe. In connection with the growing number of prison population, the issue of so-called prison violence, including implementation, also comes to the fore possible preventive interventions and measures (including psychiatric examination prisoners, individual emotion management programs, etc.) (Juříček, Smolík, 2023).

Structure and placement of primary expertise training of diverse types:

- A – type focused on members of the Prison Services of Czech Republic without differences in their placement. The education and training for a member takes up to 15 weeks including the final exam when the member must prove their theoretical knowledge in areas of education, prison politics, ethical norms, psychology, and practice such as checks, handling handcuffs, and manipulation with weapon.
- B1 – this type is aimed for employees who are in contacts with prisoners, but they do not run any handling programs. Typically, these are people who take care of logistics. This course takes one week and finished with written exam.
- B2 – this course is focused on employees who are in contact with prisoners, and they run the handling programs. These are often people who secure the detention sentences such as psychologists, specialised pedagogues, social workers, and sometimes sociologists. The education of these professions is focused not only on theoretical education but also on practical skills required for their ability to perform this job. Mainly this includes preparation and leading of the program, evaluation of the sentenced people knowledge of diagnostical tools and method used during preparation of diagnostical files, and methods of working with specific groups of prisoners. This course takes up to eight weeks and it is finished with verbal exam from chosen subjects in front of groups of experts.
- B3 – this type of course is aimed on medical staff including doctors and nurses. It takes up to one week and it is finished by written exam.
- B4 – this course is focused on civic employees working part-time but they work in direct contact with prisoners.
- I – the new employees' course which is focused on employees who will not work in direct contact with prisoners. These include assistant or employees who will work in economic resorts or maintenance resorts. This course is not conducted in person, but the preparation happens individually. Every employee is given the distance texts which help them to prepare for the exam.

The base of each organisation are specifically trained employees and thus every step taken by an organisation should be focused on its employees.

It is necessary to mention the aspect of professional practice and professional training, as stated by Stárek, Klugerová, Víšek (2022). The development and nature of quality work placement is not only the work of the university but also each student, specifically from the perspective of representation of the given university when a student creates the first impression not only in itself but also in the university itself and may thus open or close the gates to undertaking further work placement. The ever-expanding portfolio of institutions with which they collaborate or participate in project activities, conferences, professional seminars generates awareness of the diversity of the profession, but also the interconnectedness and transfer of information that evaluates the student, the university and their expertise or performance.

Therefore, if the Prison Services of Czech Republic should be able to be an effective and efficient social service, they should be able to rely on its employees. These employees should be experts in their field, and they should be able to prepare the programs for sentenced people that prepare them for their life after their imprisonment finishes. The head of Academy acknowledges this need, and they aim to continue to prepare their employees so they can help to prisoners to re-socialise. Further, they keep educating their current employees.

Radicalization and extremist expressions represent a significant security threat to the prison environment, especially in relation to its specificity. The dynamic nature of the radicalization process in connection with the mutual influence of processes in the outside society on the prison environment and vice versa causes the radicalization process to take on new forms (not only) in the prison environment. In this context, it is important to monitor these manifestations, whether with regard to the activities carried out, the penetration of illegal substances and objects, or symbolism (Lochmannová, Kolář, 2021).

It is necessary to realize that radicalization is a multifactorial problem, therefore it should be experts from the ranks of psychologists, pedagogues, sociologists, etc. were also to participate in education. However, the Prison Service of the Czech Republic does not have such a large number of experts who would be able to educate employees in these areas. For that reason, it is necessary to educational activities also included experts from the academic sphere, who will not only able to speak about the topic in depth, but who will be willing to be educated participate and share information with representatives of the given security corps. Sometimes, however the sharing of information and experience between security forces can appear as problematic, mainly due to various security checks (Vejvodová, Kolář, 2019).

Requirements for the training of security specialists, which also takes in the field of emergency management and protection of the public, are changing in response to the changing needs of society. The Czech Republic, acting through its competent ministries, has developed a Concept of Education in emergency Management which was approved by the National Security Council in 2001. Over time, however, these provisions have lost some of their relevance given the needs and rapidly changing demands of society and the security situation. The analysis that has been carried out has confirmed a lack of interconnection and uniformity within educational activities. Therefore, the plan of non-legislative governmental tasks adopted by the Czech Republic for the first half of 2017

aimed to optimise the rules for the training of specialists to bring them into line with current trends and needs. The aim of the updated provision was, in addition to the training of emergency management specialists, to enhance the co-ordination of educational processes, to provide consequent regular information support to trainers, and to provide the opportunity of acquiring lecturing skills and teaching experience. Subsequently, some concerns were voiced that target groups might not be interested in this training, and that the budget for this sector would be reduced. At present, however, adequate systematic branch management is currently lacking in this area in terms of both scale and continuity. The present chapter outlines the gradual development of the education system in emergency management and offers a comparison of educational concepts, emphasising their positive and negative aspects (Tušer et al., 2022).

5. Conclusion

The Prison Service of Czech Republic in part of security armed corps which secure the prisons, detention prisons, and institutes of detention. Further, their aim is to protect the society against the delinquents. Next crucial aim is to prepare sentenced people for their return to society. To fulfil these goals the employees, prepare handling programs that combine diverse activities which should prepare prisoners for their life after their release.

Through completing their aims employees must respect prisoners' rights and dignity and that must happen without regards to their sentence or crime they have conducted. Furthermore, they must secure safe and dignified environment for all prisoners. The employees should also look after prisoners mental and physical health.

An important aspect of prison environment is violence and conflicts prevention. The prevention is secured through diverse prevention programs and activities which aims to support positive interpersonal relationships and it helps to solve problems in constructive way.

The Prison Service of Czech Republic cooperates with other institutions and organisation such as probation and media services, non-state non-profit companies and volunteering so that they can provide complex support to prisoners during their return to society.

The part of prison system is care for specific groups of prisoners such as young prisoners, prisoners with mental disability, or prisoners with health disability. This care is focused on diverse individual needs of prisoners and provides it with respects to legal norms and international standards of human rights. Further, the individualised approach towards prisoners' needs is stressed. Throughout this the system aims to support individuals more effectively and efficiently. So, their re-socialisation is successful.

Societies' trends are willing to minimize stigmatisation of prisoners and support for their integration to society after their release which requires cooperation of prison system with public and support of public understanding without assumptions and discrimination. Similarly, it is crucial that the prison services keep monitoring and analysing

development of crime, and crime behaviour so that they can react to new challenges and needs in area of imprisonment.

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